

CLINICAL AND IMMUNOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF STABLE ANGINA PECTORIS IN ELDERLY WOMEN WITH CONCOMITANT ARTERIAL HYPERTENSION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15653964>

Annotation

A comprehensive examination of 208 elderly women (60-74 years; mean age 66.0 ± 6.0 years) with ischemic heart disease and arterial hypertension of II-III degrees was conducted. The main group consisted of patients with stable angina pectoris (SS) of functional classes I-III: FC-1-58 (32.6%), FC-2 — 62 (34.8%), FC-3 — 58 (32.6%). The comparison group included 30 patients with progressive angina pectoris. Clinical, biochemical and immunological parameters were studied. The relationship between the level of cytokines and the severity of the disease was revealed. Prognostic criteria for the course of SS in elderly women with hypertension have been developed, which help clarify the diagnosis and individualize therapy.

Keywords

Stable angina, arterial hypertension, elderly women, cytokines, immunological indicators, prognosis, diagnosis.

Relevance

The combination of stable angina and arterial hypertension in elderly women is a complex clinical and diagnostic problem due to progressive vascular and immunological disorders. According to epidemiological studies, more than 65% of women over 60 years of age suffer from hypertension, and symptoms of stable angina occur in 25-30% of this population. Age-related changes in the immune system, an imbalance in the cytokine profile, and the severity of endothelial dysfunction contribute to the aggravation of the clinical course of coronary heart disease. At the same time, clear prognostic immunological criteria for assessing the severity of stable angina in elderly women with arterial hypertension have not been developed. This determines the need for a comprehensive assessment of clinical, biochemical and immunological parameters, which will improve risk stratification, increase the diagnostic value of the examination and individualize therapeutic approaches for this category of patients, reducing the risk of cardiovascular complications and disease progression.

Research objective

Comprehensive clinical and immunological diagnostics of stable angina pectoris in elderly women with arterial hypertension and development of prognostic criteria for its severity.

Materials and methods

The study included 208 women with IHD and grade II–III arterial hypertension aged 60–74 years (mean age 66.0 ± 6.0 years). The main group consisted of patients with stable angina: FC-1–58 (32.6%), FC-2 — 62 (34.8%), FC-3 — 58 (32.6%). The comparison group consisted of 30 women with progressive angina pectoris. Clinical and instrumental data, peripheral blood parameters, biochemical status, cytokine levels (IL-6, TNF- α), CIC, and the content of lymphocytic subpopulations were studied. General clinical, anthropometric, biochemical, immunological, functional and statistical research methods were used.

Results

In women with stable FC-3 angina, a significant increase in the level of IL-6 to 15.2 ± 1.4 pg/ml and TNF- α to 19.7 ± 1.6 pg/ml was detected compared to FC-1 (IL-6 — 8.6 ± 0.9 pg/ml, TNF- α — 11.2 ± 1.3 pg/ml).ml; $p < 0.01$). The CIC level was maximal in FC-3 — 123.4 ± 5.2 U/ ml versus 84.6 ± 4.3 U/ ml in FC-1 ($p < 0.05$). The CD4+/CD8+ index increased with the progression of angina pectoris FC (up to 2.8 ± 0.2 ; $p < 0.05$). Significant correlations were found between immune markers and clinical manifestations of the disease ($r = 0.62$ – 0.68 ; $p < 0.01$).

Conclusion

In elderly women with stable angina pectoris and grade II–III arterial hypertension, pronounced immune disorders were detected: activation of pro-inflammatory cytokines (IL-6, TNF- α), increased CIC levels, and shifts in subpopulations of T-lymphocyte subpopulations. The severity of these changes depended on the functional class of angina pectoris, which allows us to use them as prognostic markers of the severity of the disease. The developed clinical and immunological indicators increase the informative value of diagnostics, contribute to more accurate risk stratification and individualization of treatment of patients in this category. The results of the study are recommended for implementation in practical healthcare in the examination of elderly women with CHD and hypertension.

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